

MEDICAL SCIENCES

SPECIFIC POST-RESECTION COMPLICATIONS OF LIVER RESECTIONS WITH DIFFERENT CLAMPING TECHNIQUES

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Abstract

Liver resection remains one of the most technically challenging surgical procedure in abdominal surgery due to the complex anatomical arrangement in the liver

The development of new intraoperative techniques, as well as increased knowledge of the anatomy and pathophysiology of the liver after hepatectomy, have contributed to the reduction of postoperative complications.

Keywords: liver resections, complications after liver resections, clamping techniques.

Introduction

The reasons for the rapid development of liver resection surgery are due to the advancement of anatomical knowledge of segmental liver anatomy, the development of parenchymal dissection techniques, and definitive hemo- and biliostasis.

Objective

Clamping techniques reduce the volume of intraoperative blood loss, but is this associated with a higher risk of early specific post-resection complications?

Materials and methods

For the period from January, 2007 - March, 2018 in Clinic of liver, biliary pancreatic and general surgery, Acibadem City Clinic Tokuda Hospital ,1021 interventions were performed on the liver:

- for different indications, and different types of procedures;
- in varying volume and varying degrees of complexity;
- with different technical characteristics.

A single-center, retrospective study was conducted.

Cases of intervention other than liver resection by

definition were excluded ISGLS, "removal of part of the liver parenchyma due to involvement by a disease process or traumatic injury resulting in devitalization of the parenchyma".

Thus, the study did not find the cases of:

- hepatotomy;
- cystotomies and cyst resections, practically without removal of functioning or pathologically altered liver parenchyma;
- liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors. liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors;
- interruption of trunk branches of the hepatic artery and/or portal vein with the aim of hypoperfusion of a given area (segments, lobe);
- suture of the liver in trauma;

Thus, a total of 852 cases of liver resections were included in the series

Results

Statistically reliable ($p < 0.001$) application of the clamping method was reported less frequently in Atypical liver resections both as an independent intervention and as an element of multivisceral resection, respectively. 12.8% and 8.7%, while in Anatomical liver resections, these percentages were 50.0% and 38.6% (table 1).

Table.1

The application of clamping technique in Anatomic and Atypical liver resections.

Another operation	clamping	Statistics	Anatomic resection	Atypical resection	Total	p
No	No	N	58	191	249	<0,001
		%	50,0%	87,2%	74,3%	
	Yes	N	58	28	86	
		%	50,0%	12,8%	25,7%	
Yes	No	N	70	369	439	<0,001
		%	61,4%	91,3%	84,7%	
	Yes	N	44	35	79	
		%	38,6%	8,7%	15,3%	

The amount of intraoperative blood loss varied in a fairly wide range according to the type of resection (Table 2). In Atypical liver resections, the average blood loss was less - 97.14ml (20-500ml), and in Anatomical resections, it was 51.0% more, 147.30ml (40-800ml).[1-15]

Table 2.

Intraoperative blood loss in Anatomic and Atypical liver resections.

Type of resection	N	Blood loss (ml)				
		Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max
Anatomic resection	230	147,30	100,00	101,22	40,00	800,00
Atypical resection	622	97,14	100,00	63,53	20,00	500,00

Discussion

The control of intraoperative bleeding, resp. the reduction of blood loss is essential for a shorter duration of surgery, "less anesthesia time", a reduction in the need for hemotransfusions, which is with a reduced risk of hemorrhages and other specific post-resection complications in the early postoperative period, as well as more good long-term results in oncological cases.

Conclusion

Clamping techniques contribute to warm ischemia of both the "falling" and the residual portion of the liver. This, against the background of cirrhosis, steatosis, drug-induced toxic damage, has an adverse effect on hepatocyte function in the early postoperative period, on regenerative-reparative processes and logically increases the risk of specific post-resection complications

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